

Practitioner inquiry: A year-long project in Taiwanese Waldorf schools

Neil Boland, Hornfay Cherng, Hsiaohua Hsueh and Chih-Hung Wang

Introduction

In recent years, colleagues in the Taiwanese Waldorf movement have been considering a question that has likely been asked by many groups around the world: how can Waldorf teaching practice continue to evolve in ways that meet today's students, current conditions and the changing demands placed on teachers? As one colleague put it, "I have always believed that the Waldorf circle needs research momentum, especially in the classroom." Waldorf schools in Taiwan have been established now for nearly three decades – long enough for traditions, habits and inherited practices to become well established. Many of these practices can be traced back to times and places far removed from twenty-first-century Taiwan, and some teachers and members of the national Federation began to wonder whether an intentional process of inquiry might help address this.

This led to the establishment in 2024 of a joint initiative of the Taiwanese Federation of Waldorf Schools and staff from the Center for Waldorf Education in the National Tsing Hua University. The intention was to create a forum in which teachers would be encouraged and supported to look more closely at their own practice through small, manageable cycles of trial and reflection, perhaps best described as teacher inquiry informed by action research.

This is important for Waldorf education, because it looks beyond inherited practices, to the capacity of teachers to meet and respond to the children in front of them. As schools become more established, there is a risk that familiar forms are repeated without being sufficiently questioned. Providing a structure for teachers to look carefully at their own practice can help keep the education responsive and connected to the realities of contemporary Taiwan.

One participant observed, "I think every teacher is already doing action research, but everyday work and life so easily crowd everything out, and ideas quickly fade with time."

In this sense, the initiative offered a structure and support to a process that already belongs to the everyday work of teachers. It also recalls a working method of the early Waldorf faculty meetings, where practical questions from the classroom were repeatedly brought into the teachers' meeting, considered together, and then taken back into practice (see GA 300a–c). Viewed from this angle, this Taiwanese initiative also represents a contemporary expression of an established Waldorf tradition. At the same time, it was a response to a practical need for connection across schools: "Every school could work independently, of course, but if we were all working in isolated pockets without a platform to understand what others were doing, these efforts might dissipate like 'little sparks'." Not every project followed a formal action research methodology, but they all shared the common cycle of trial, observation and reflection characteristic of practitioner inquiry.

Project design

The project is an example of what can be achieved through collaboration between a national federation of Waldorf schools and university staff. It took the form of a year-long, voluntary community of research practice in 2024–2025, involving around 20 teachers from several Waldorf schools across Taiwan and staff from the Center for Waldorf Education. Each participant identified an aspect of their teaching that they wanted to explore more deeply. Some revisited a main lesson block or curriculum area. Others focused on questions arising from student needs, feedback from alumni or established activities such as class plays or trips.

Although the project was planned and led by academics, the emphasis was not on formal academic outputs. Instead, the project encouraged teachers to set up a cycle of inquiry. After deciding on a question, they tried something new, observed how it unfolded in practice, documented what happened in some form (e.g. a journal, vlog, audio files or photos) and then reflected on how these observations might inform what came next.

In addition to this, the Federation hoped that bringing teachers together from schools in different parts of the country would create a kind of professional community that rarely happens in everyday school life. “I had already mentioned ... that perhaps the Federation could form a ‘Classroom Research’ organisation or journal, where teachers’ research could be published and inspire others.” After a face-to-face meeting over a weekend in Taipei, monthly meetings were held online for practicality. These acted as check-ins in which teachers presented their interim findings to each other, asked questions and offered each other support. These meetings had the twofold advantage of bringing a degree of accountability, while also being productive: “the pressure encourages us to take action,” as one participant put it.

A number of small, facilitated focus groups were held after the project ended, involving teachers from selected groups. These discussions were recorded, transcribed and analysed thematically. The quotations included here are drawn directly from these conversations and represent participants’ reflections on their experiences of the process.

The project was intentionally modest with the single aim to see whether supporting small cycles of inquiry could help teachers understand their practice better and encourage innovations which would respond more consciously to the needs of their students.

The importance of community

During the year-long project, it became clear that its social, supportive nature was a strong motivation for teachers to continue, sometimes even more than the individual projects themselves. The monthly meetings formed a rhythm but also a subtle pressure. Every month, a small number of groups presented their interim findings to the larger group, helping maintain momentum even when people’s time was short. Several teachers noted that they might not have continued on their own without this external accountability and support.

Because many Waldorf teachers work largely independently, there are seldom opportunities for regular, structured conversations with teachers from other schools. The meetings created a space in which teachers could observe how others were dealing with similar challenges, ask questions they might otherwise not have asked and recognise that others were facing similar struggles. As one participant reflected, “In the earliest exchanges, I found that, as well as my project, there were many topics ... that I found fascinating and truly worth doing.” One participant described the value of “hearing other people’s plans and ideas,” while another noted that “listening to colleagues from other schools was very rewarding.”

The project also suggested that teacher inquiry could become a means of connection across the national movement. Without such structures, local initiatives risk remaining isolated: “Every school could work independently, of course, but if we were all working in isolation without a platform to understand what others were doing, these efforts might dissipate like ‘little sparks’.”

At the same time, it needs to be acknowledged that participation was uneven. Time pressures, administrative work and scheduling conflicts affected attendance. These realities, especially time constraints, shaped what kinds of inquiry teachers could realistically undertake, and highlighted the importance of designing projects to fit the practical constraints of teachers’ lives. However, the shared nature of the monthly meetings encouraged participants to return to the project once their schedules allowed and pick up where they left off.

The effect of pedagogical innovation

Each teacher engaged in practical experimentation. These ranged from documenting main lesson blocks in detail to surveying alumni, from reflecting on past drama projects to reconsidering aspects of curriculum content from the point of view of localising it. For some, the decision to participate itself reflected a willingness to test something new within an already demanding workload: “So even though I was very busy, I still wanted to give it a go.”

Several teachers discovered tensions or unexpected challenges when attempting to document their practice. One found that writing up a sequence of lessons revealed gaps that they had not noticed when teaching it. Another found that alumni valued outdoor experiences and group projects over academic content, which in turn challenged previously held assumptions they had held about student development. The inquiry was guided by the pedagogical question: “How can feedback from former students improve our teaching and understanding of what contemporary high school students need – things which we might not have previously considered but could do better in future.” A third teacher took the opportunity to reconstruct what had been learned through past drama work through conversations with former students.

Not all projects were completed as intended. These are not failures but reflections of the pressures of daily teaching life. More important were the attempts to look closely at practice

and the adjustments that followed. Writing and presenting work often exposed unreflected assumptions about teachers' practice and their students' experiences.

In all cases, changes were small and incremental rather than bold or dramatic. Yet even modest changes, such as rethinking a main lesson block, revising content or revisiting well-established routines, were significant within an ongoing teaching practice.

Inquiry and the development of the teacher

A notable feature of the project was that changes in teaching practice were often accompanied by changes in teachers' self-understanding. Documenting lessons and analysing responses made aspects of practice visible that had previously gone unnoticed. As one participant reflected, "Even though my research is only half done (I still have the students' journals!), this process helped me to see my own development." Another described the same sense of change over time: "Looking back, I realised that who I was then is not the same as who I am now – my way of working has changed."

Several teachers described a change in how they understood themselves in relation to their work. This did not involve adopting a formal identity as researchers, but rather an increased awareness of how their thinking shaped what they did in the classroom. One teacher put this directly: "People who know me understand that I always have strong thoughts about the curriculum, but having opinions alone, without taking action, just makes one an annoying person – so I felt I should try to do something myself."

Teachers entered the project from different starting points. One admitted, "To be honest, when I first learned about this big project, I didn't take it very seriously because I was busy writing my master's thesis." Another recalled, "When I first heard that this project was starting, I was so excited – I felt that I had finally waited long enough." Others began with more specific intentions: "My focus at the time was mainly on the students from [my school]; I thought that, after changing things there, I could learn more about other schools." Despite these differences, participation often created a space in which teachers saw their work, and themselves, more clearly.

Because the inquiries were grounded in classroom practice, any change in practice was also a change in how teachers understood their role. The transformations were not dramatic, but suggest that paying extended attention to practice often involves a parallel movement in teacher identity.

What this suggests

Overall, the experiences of participating teachers suggest that small-scale inquiry, supported by a simple structure and a collegial environment, can deepen understanding of teaching practice. The project also highlighted the value of having a structured space for sharing observations. Presenting progress and challenges, listening to colleagues from across the country and responding to questions created a form of dialogue which rarely happens within school routines. As one participant noted, “For one thing, having some pressure helped push things along.” The regular meetings gave the work a rhythm and a degree of accountability, while still allowing each teacher’s inquiry to remain grounded in the reality of their classrooms.

The project was deliberately not framed as a conventional research project. This connected back to the Federation’s original purpose, “to encourage teachers to ‘take action’ through action research.” It suggests a broader possibility for the Waldorf movement in Taiwan, in which teacher inquiry becomes a shared cultural practice rather than the work of isolated individuals.

Time constraints were a persistent challenge and highlight the need for realistic expectations and institutional support. Future developments might include more reliable ways of sharing, such as an online archive or some form of publication.

Overall, the project suggests that inquiry-based reflection, as a community-based collaboration between national Waldorf organisations and academia, can complement existing forms of professional development in Waldorf schools. Although this kind of collaboration is still relatively unusual, but it offers something valuable to all those involved. Teachers bring the questions, experience and practical knowledge that arise from daily classroom life, while university staff can offer time, structure and research experience that teachers may not always have available within the pressures of school life. When these contributions are brought together, teacher inquiry can become more visible, resilient and easily shared across schools.

Conclusion: Beginning another round

“Once teachers experience the joy of research, schools around the country can be connected through that work.” As one participant reflected: “Our goal was never to produce a worthy collection of research papers, but to see what the Waldorf community in Taiwan could become.” Teachers’ willingness to engage during this first cycle was noteworthy. For some, the work opened new questions; for others, it clarified areas for further development. On this basis, the Taiwanese Federation and the Center for Waldorf Education have chosen to continue the initiative into a second round. It is not known what this may lead to – longer-term collaboration, new models of professional learning or something else entirely. What is already observable, however, is a growing commitment to sustained teacher inquiry as a way of renewing practice in response to students’ needs and the realities of Waldorf education in contemporary Taiwan.

Hornfay Cherng, Hsiaohua Hsueh and Zhihong Wang work in the Center for Waldorf Education at National Tsing Hua University in Hsinchu, Taiwan. Neil Boland is an adjunct professor at the university and works in the School of Education at Auckland University of Technology in Aotearoa New Zealand.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20743801>